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BIBLIOPHILE

Newsletter from the
DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE
CENTRAL UNIVERSITY OF TAMIL NADU
SPECIAL ISSUE ON PROF. S. RAVI

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Adieu

Prof. S. RAVI

Founder Head, DLIS &
Dean, School of Communication

DLIS-CUTN Fraternity

HOD's MESSAGE

FAREWELL NOTE TO PROF. S. RAVI

I am delighted to write about Prof. S. Ravi on his superannuation from the active service on October 31, 2022 from the Department of Library & Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur. I pray to GOD for your sound health, joy, and peace for future endeavour. I am aware that you have made significant contributions to the development of the library and information science profession in numerous ways throughout your lengthy academic career. The DDE of Annamalai University reached every part of the nation under your inspiring leadership. You expressed a desire to contribute your assistance and knowledge in setting up the recently established Department at CUTN. Your knowledge and persistent efforts to build the Department of LIS@CUTN from the ground up are commendable. You have been really helpful to me in many ways since I joined and in the management of the Department. I'm happy to work with

you at DLIS CUTN. For your dedication to the Department and University, I would like to express my deepest gratitude, love, and appreciation. I appreciate your continued support of our team and your positive attitude. We will miss you! Retirement is the reward you get for putting up with co-workers like me for many years. I wish you the best!

Thank You.

Dr. AKHANDANAND SHUKLA

Dr. Akhandanand Shukla

Associate Professor & Head
DLIS, CUTN

SABA SHREERAM P

M. Lib. I. Sc- II Year
Central University of Tamil Nadu

STUDENT EDITOR'S NOTE

I am so glad that I got an opportunity to be one of Prof. S. Ravi Sir's students. He has always been an inspiration to every LIS students. He never fails to appreciate and encourage the young talents. I've learned so much outside the curriculum from him especially how to treat every individual with respect. Even after his retirement, the positive impact he created in the field of DLIS, will always remain permanent. I would like to thank Dr. K. G. Sudhier for giving me an opportunity to be the student editor of the special edition of Bibliophile.

SABA SHREERAM P

VICE CHANCELLOR'S MESSAGE

பேராசிரியர். மு. கிருஷ்ணன்
துணை வேந்தர்

प्रो. एम. कृष्णन्
कुलपति

Prof. M. Krishnan
Vice Chancellor

தமிழ்நாடு மத்தியப் பல்கலைக்கழகம்

तमिलनाडु केंद्रीय विश्वविद्यालय

(संसद द्वारा पारित अधिनियम 2009 के अंतर्गत स्थापित)

CENTRAL UNIVERSITY OF TAMIL NADU

(Established by an Act of Parliament, 2009)

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Message from the Vice-Chancellor, Central University of Tamil Nadu on the Superannuation of Prof. S. Ravi, Department of Library & Information Science

I am very happy to honor Prof. S. Ravi, on this day of his retirement, who has served in Central University of Tamil Nadu and contributed a lot to the development of the University. In his long academic career, he has contributed immensely for the development of Library and Information Science.

Under his Leadership, the Department has become a very successful one. He has contributed significantly to the expansion and progress of the field and will be remembered for it in the years to come. My sincere thanks for his selfless service to the University.

For his dedication and hard work, he deserves the best retirement ever. I wish him good health, happiness and peace in his retirement life.

I appreciate the Department of Library and Information Science, CUTN for organizing the felicitation ceremony of Prof. S. Ravi, properly by publishing a special edition of the Departmental Newsletter, Bibliophile.

Prof. M. Krishnan
Vice-Chancellor

FORMER VC'S MESSAGE

Prof A.P. Dash

Ph.D., D.Sc., F.N.A.Sc., F.A.M.S., F.N.E.S.A., F.Z.S.I., F.I.S.C.D.

President, National Academy of Vector Borne Diseases

Vice Chancellor, AIPH University

Ex-VICE CHANCELLOR, CENTRAL UNIVERSITY OF Tamil Nadu

Ex-Adviser, World Health Organisation

Formerly:

Director, National Institute of Malaria Research, New Delhi

Director, Institute of Life Sciences, Bhubaneswar

Director, National Institute for Research on Tribal Health, Jabalpur

Director, Desert Medicine Research Centre, Jodhpur

Director, Centre for Research in Medical Entomology, Madurai

Date: 8th October, 2022

MESSAGE

It is my honour and pleasure to write about Prof. S. Ravi, on the occasion of his superannuation from the Central University of Tamil Nadu on 31 st October 2022. Let me wish you good health, happiness, peace and pleasure filled days ahead. During this long journey you have contributed immensely to the growth and development of Library and Information Science.

On the eve of relieving as the founder Head, Dept. of Library & Information Science (DLIS) and Dean, School of Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, I wish to convey my sincere gratitude and love for your guidance and service to the University. I feel proud to be associated with you at CUTN and you have supported me immensely in different roles. I thank you for all the help and support that you have offered to me.

Your 5+ years stint as the Professor and Dean at CUTN, has led the Department and the University to achieving new heights. The DLIS of CUTN has been one of the highly productive and visible department in the country under your headship. You have contributed a lot for the growth and development of the DLIS for which you will be remembered in the days to come. God bless you and your family with good health, lots of happiness and a peaceful life in the coming years.

I congratulate the Dept. of Library & Information Science, CUTN for aptly planning to organise the felicitation function of Prof. S. Ravi befittingly by publishing special issue of the Department Newsletter- Bibliophile.

Thank You.

Regards,

A. P. Dash

FACULTY EDITOR'S PAGE

PROF. S. RAVI- A CHAMPION OF CAUSE! ADIEU AND THANKS...

The current issue of the Bibliophile has bestowed upon me the honour of putting up a befitting tribute for Prof. Sabanayagam Ravi, a dedicated and competent colleague of ours, in the CUTN. Being the Faculty Editor of this Newsletter gives me immense pleasure and pride to mark the glorious career of Prof. S. Ravi.

For this special issue, we have contacted eminent LIS professionals and faculty members of LIS schools from all over the country and unsurprisingly, the response was overwhelming. This is testimonial in Prof. Ravi's acceptance and respect that he has earned over the years around his colleagues, friends and well wishers.

Prof. Ravi has been a popular name in the LIS domain for over a decade and I remember meeting him for the first time at the University of Kerala, where he addressed us at the Prof. K. A. Issac memorial lecture organised by the Kerala Library Association (KLA). His presence in my academic career was inevitable and he was a great source of comfort and support in this University. There were several teachers, professionals and colleagues throughout my career and Prof. Ravi stood out as an energising, encouraging, affectionate

Dr. K. G. SUDHIER

Assistant Professor
DLIS, CUTN

and caring towards his subordinates and associates. He has been of great help to several people on a professional and personal level.

A great orator and a singer, one could find the professor grooving to old Tamil songs. Prof. Ravi has demonstrated his leadership by taking responsibility for starting a new department in CUTN, Thiruvapur, the birthplace of Dr. S. R. Ranganathan. We are fortunate to have such a guide and mentor; without whom we wouldn't have achieved the progress and developmental growth of our Department within such a short period. I am a proud associate of him and I consider myself lucky to be a part of the innings that had its inception at this University. He has been a source of inspiration and encouragement throughout my career at CUTN. He has pushed me through my career and has motivated me to explore unexplored territories. A simple thank you wouldn't suffice for all that he has done for the department, but this opportunity serves me right to honour and wish Prof. Ravi the very best for his future on behalf of DLIS-CUTN. I wish him further success in all his endeavours and pray Lord Nataraja (Chidambaram) for a long, peaceful and healthy life.

This issue wouldn't be realty if not for all the contributors, facilitators and all those who supported us in bringing out this significant issue of Bibliophile.

K. G. SUDHIER

MOB. 9446484561

NSD DIRECTOR's (i/c) MESSAGE

प्रोफेसर रमेश चन्द्र गौड़
निदेशक (पुस्तकालय और सूचना) एवं विभागाध्यक्ष

Professor Ramesh C. Gaur
Ph.D., Fulbright Scholar (Virginia Tech., USA)
Director (Lib. & Inf.) & Head -Kala Nidhi
Dean, IGNCA

आजादी का
अमृत महोत्सव

कलानिधि

इन्दिरा गांधी राष्ट्रीय कला केन्द्र

Kala Nidhi

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13th October, 2022

MESSAGE

I am happy that a special issue of the Newsletter- *Bibliophile* is being brought out by the Dept. of Library & Information Science (DLIS), Central University of Tamil Nadu (CUTN) on the occasion of the superannuation of Prof. S. Ravi, founder Head, DLIS and Dean, School of Communication, CUTN.

I am sure this special issue containing messages, articles and reminiscences from learned professors in LIS and librarians will be helpful to budding professionals and faculties and, therefore, will be a rich contribution to the LIS literature.

His contribution to the field of LIS as a teacher, research supervisor and as member of various bodies is always appreciable. He had shown leadership, ability and enthusiasm in all the fields of activity he engaged in. He has contributed immensely to developing the DLIS, CUTN as full fledged department. His passion for the promotion of teaching and research has earned him the respect and admiration of students and colleagues.

I believe this Newsletter brought out in honour of Prof. S. Ravi is a befitting acknowledgement of his glorious, dedicated and long career. So, it is my pleasure to write this message, and I wish him every success in all his academic and professional endeavours.

Thank you.

RAMESH C. GAUR

Director (Additional Charge), National School of Drama

MEMOIR OF A CLASSMATE

I feel extremely happy to share my memoir associated with Prof. S. Ravi, who is retiring after four decades of sincere teaching and administrative service at Annamalai University, Chidambaram, and Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvavur. We were classmates for the PG program in LIS at Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai during 1988-89. Prof. S. Ravi is a very sincere and hard worker in his studies. He used to refer to many additional books from the library for the coursework. Lover of old classical songs and classical movies. I had a chance to visit Kodaikanal hills along with him. We also visited Thiruparankundram hill and climbed up to the top of the hill. Those days are golden days for us.

I wish him a happy, healthy and peaceful retired life.

Dr.R.Parameswaran

Dr. R. Parameswaran
 Librarian
 Central University of Tamil Nadu

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 FACULTY EDITOR

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PROF. S. RAVI : A PROFILE

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Prof. S. Ravi, M.A., M.L.I.Sc., Ph.D

Eleven years of professional experience at the University Library and 33 years of experience in post graduate teaching, research and academic administration with **16 years as Professor** in Annamalai University and also in the Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvapur.

Mentor, Commonwealth Diploma in Youth Development Work Programme offered in collaboration with Annamalai University and the Commonwealth Secretariat, London with **Dual Certification**.

Under his guidance **22** candidates were awarded **Ph.D** and **52** candidates have been awarded M.Phil.

Ph.D. Thesis Adjudicated and Viva Voce Examination conducted - 200

Invited Talk - 70

Member in Selection Committee - 39

Paper Presented / Participated in National and International Conference / Seminar -90

Chapter in Books - 50

Certificate of Merit and One Time Cash Award from Annamalai University.

Best Teacher Award from Annamalai University, Society for the Advancement of Library and Information Science (SALIS) and Madras Library Association (MALA). Life Time Achievement Award from Madras Library Association (MALA).

Life Time Achievement Award from Madras Library Association (MALA).

Published 3 books, Edited 9 books and 50 Articles in National and International Journals.

Visited Australia, Singapore, Malaysia, Mauritius, United Arab Emirates, Thailand, Brunei and Sri Lanka for academic purposes.

Member in several State, National and International Professional Organizations.

ANNAMALAI UNIVERSITY, CHIDAMBARAM

Faculty in the Department of Library and Information Science from September 1989 to October 1997

Deputy Coordinator, UGC-SAP DRS-I Programme

Coordinator, Professor and Head, Library and Information Science Wing, Directorate of Distance Education from November 1997 to June 2017

Member : Academic Council, Board of Studies and Faculty of Arts

In Charge Distance Education Cell (DEC), **Coordinator**, Internal Quality Assurance Cell (DDE-IQAC), **Coordinator**, DDE NAAC Peer Team Committee

CENTRAL UNIVERSITY OF TAMILNADU, THIRUVARUR

Professor and Head, Department of Library and Information Science

Dean, School of Communication

Chairperson: Board of Studies, School Board, School of Communication

Chairperson: IQAC Committee for Teaching, Learning and Evaluation

Convener, Committee for NIRF - Research and Professional Practice

Co-ordinator, CUCET Examinations

Member: Court, Executive Council, Academic Council, IQAC, Library Advisory Committee, University Admission Steering Committee, Convocation Committee, Editorial Committee for the preparation of Annual Report, Committee for the University Decennial Publications, Board of Studies in Media and Communication, Community College and Committee for the Empanelment of Purchase of Printed Books and Subscription of Journals, Central Library.

Chairman: Committee for sharing of E-Resources to Madras School of Economics.

In-charge, Project Cell

Nodal Officer: Central University Portal and UGC University Activity Monitoring Portal.

Chairman, Students Grievance Redressal Committee

Chief Vigilance Officer - (Part-time)

Member, NAAC Peer Team Committee.

Nominee Chairman, Kendriya Vidyalaya School Management Committee.

Presently working as **Professor** in the Department of Library and Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvavarur since 2017, will be retiring after completing **44 years** of service on 31st October 2022

I AM NOT ALONE

It is very heartening to write this note on the eve of the superannuation of one of the most warm and affable academics at CUTN. When I joined the CUTN's Dept. of Media and Communication in 2020, Prof. S. Ravi was the Dean of the School of Communication.

He provided great moral support throughout his tenure in my initiatives to revamp the syllabi of the MA and PhD programmes and the starting of the Critical Communication Studies Lecture Series (CCSLS). He always had words of praise and encouragement which meant a lot to me as they were from an academic with nearly four decades of experience as a researcher and teacher. His passion for contributing to his chosen discipline, Library and Information Science, is remarkable and his services to his discipline are acknowledged as peerless. I am sure this will be evident in the grand farewell function that is being organised in CUTN wherein academics from across India will be present to honour him, recall their associations with him as their most cherished benefactor.

Prof. G. Ravindran

Dean, School of
Communication &
Head, Dept. of Media
& Communication

அரியவற்றுள்ளெல்லாம் அரிதே பெரியாரைப்
பேணித்த மரக்கொளல். (443)

It is a good fortune that my friendship with Prof. Ravi is in accordance with this Kural. Yesterday (17.10.2022), I happened to see Prof. Ravi with a group of academics in the lounge of the VC's secretariat. They were in CUTN to make arrangements for the grand farewell function on 30th October 2022. They were introduced by Prof. Ravi as his former students. They are now serving as senior faculty members in Annamalai University and other universities. It was heartwarming to learn that the former students of Prof. Ravi are having the rarest of rare possession in their lives, that is the friendship of their teacher, mentor and friend. It was a moment to remind myself about Kural 443's relevance in reality in the lives of many of his former students, friends and well wishers. I am not alone.

Wishes to the next innings of life...

Prof. (Dr) Ravinder Kumar
Chadha

Tagore National Fellow for Cultural
Research
Ex- Additional Secretary,
Parliament of India

Ex- Prof & Dean,
Malwanchal University.

Ex-Faculty
Banasthali Vidyapith University

Today's no ordinary day because today my dearest friend Prof S Ravi after the completion of 40 years of glorious service to the nation and the LIS Profession has reached another major life milestone that marks the ending of one chapter and the start of another. Retirement may be an ending of the 9 to 5 routine, but it is also a new beginning. It's the time to come out from the long hours at the university, for never-ending days of playing tennis, travelling and adoring the grandchildren. I am sure you also must be looking forward to having time for yourself, your prayers and self-actualisation. However, leaving

the workplace behind can also be a bittersweet time for a retiree as feelings of excitement and trepidation mix together as they look back upon the memories of their career while facing the endless possibilities ahead of them.

It's the beginning of a new inning of life that brings perfect moments for reflection and relaxation as well as spending more quality time with your loved ones. As you embark on your retirement journey, there is no doubt that you will be riddled with mixed emotions. You'll feel excited about the new opportunities and challenges that await you in this next chapter of life, but at the same time, it can be hard to say goodbye to a life's worth of memories and relationships. Your retirement day is perfect to reiterate how much you mean to me. You're a true, kind, genuine, affectionate, helpful person with a heart of gold.

A true, loyal, and trustworthy friend like you is the ultimate blessing a person could wish for. I truly am the luckiest person to have a blessed friend in you. Thank you for always sticking by my side, bestie. My dear, you are among the most respected and followed professor in the country. You have every quality to be praised for. Cheers to a professor who teaches from the heart and mind, and not just from the written notes and books. You are honest, dedicated, focused, friendly & hard-working. Professors like you add tradition and legacy to the walls of our profession. I am proud to be your friend. People like you should be given humanity's greatest honour because your life's purpose and motto truly are "Change the world through education". Most professors just teach the syllabus, but you are also an expert in two more subjects- Motivation and Inspiration – which you give to your students. Here's to you, our friendship, and many more long years of making wonderful memories together. My sincere wishes for the happiest next inning of life, my dear friend Prof S Ravi.

GALLERY

EVENTS @ CUTN

A Friend in need is a Friend Indeed...

“True great friends are hard to find, difficult to leave and impossible to forget.”

-Anon

Prof. C. R. Karisiddappa
Former Professor and Chairman
Emeritus Professor (2008-2010)
Visiting Professor (2011-2015)
Dept. of Library and Information
Science
Karnataka University, Dharwad

Every profession unknowingly brings people together to form unusual friendships. One such professional friendship brewed between Dr S Ravi and me more than 3 decades ago in Annamalai University. It's an established fact that Annamalai University distance education programs have reached the peak of popularity and the enrolments in all disciplines has increased in leaps and bounds. Library and Information Science Courses were no exceptions.

During the last decade of the 20th century, I was inducted into the Board of Examinations and for one term to the Board of Studies for the regular LIS programme at Annamalai University. During the meetings of BOE and BOS I used to meet and interact with the teaching staff of both regular course and distance education programmes. As I remember, this department was having record number of teachers. I was surprised to know about this later when I was given to understand the huge workload and the multiple tasks the teaching faculty used to undertake. Frequent visits to Annamalai University helped me to get better acquaintance with some of the vibrant teachers who were totally devoted to bring credentials to the LIS programs. One such young and energetic teacher who attracted my attention was Dr S Ravi. I was totally overtaken by his ever-smiling face, fluent language skills and the numerous tasks he used to carry out for the successful completion of the courses and his involvement in the process of all the assigned tasks relentlessly.

Though our interactions were very much limited, we used to avail every opportunity to participate in conferences and seminars wherein we tried our best to make our presence felt and our voices heard in the meetings.

Our friendship strengthened when we participated together in the International Conference on Scientometrics and Informetrics held at the University of New South Wales, Sydney, Australia, during July 2001. We spent good time in getting to know each other well. Though there was a sizable number of participants from India, only few teachers like us were given accommodation in the students' hostel on the university campus. It was a blessing in disguise to be at the same place which enabled us to go to the conference venue together and spend our evening time in search of Indian restaurant for dinner. In the process we discussed the vital role of the growing subjects like Scientometrics and Informetrics for measuring the valuechain of large-scale output of intellectual capital. This international conference indeed was beneficial to me in several ways. I was able to take the life membership of ISSI and met recognized experts in the field. It also enabled me to become aware of the visible contributions of Indian experts. More than anything, it was understanding deeply the versatility of Dr Ravi and my own research scholar, Dr B M Gupta. To my good fortune I was sponsored by 'India Focus Group'

to visit Melbourne and Canberra to deliver lectures in two of their universities. So, I was to leave for Melbourne the following day, early in the morning. The taxi to drop me at airport was arranged by the organizers on my request. But the major problem was to be present in the specified place at 4.00 a.m. There was no other way left for me except requesting Dr Ravi to help during that critical hour of need. Dr Ravi understood my anxiety, led me to the taxi stand and saw that I safely got into a taxi to go to the airport. At the same time, he monitored my journey and guided me to complete the assignments successfully. That moment taught me the value of real friendship. This is how the truth of the adage 'A Friend in need is a friend indeed' was realized by me. Our bond of friendship brought us still closer to work together in all our professional activities. Dr Ravi is a twice blessed professional. His services in Annamalai University are ever remembered by his past students for his yeomen services. Soon after the retirement at the age of 60 in Annamalai University, he was selected by the Tamil Nadu Central University to lead the newly established Department of Library and Information Science. Dr Ravi with his rich experience in both the streams of LIS Education, was able to develop the new department on par with the older established departments in the country.

As a dynamic leader, he was able to guide the new university and played multiple roles such as Dean, Faculty of Communication, and member of several high-power bodies of the university. At the same time Dr Ravi is known for his innovative experiments in LIS teaching-learning, in starting a unique comprehensive newsletter titled 'Bibliophile' which is a first of its kind in LIS departments of Indian Universities. His ripened maturity and well directed forethought have created a big avenue to the successful students coming out of the department to shape their future career. In every respect Dr Ravi, through his devoted and dedicated service has emerged as a 'Champion of Cause' as well as 'Champion of Change'.

While recording the priceless instances of my association with Dr Ravi, I acknowledge the kind gesture of Dr K G Sudhier, Faculty Editor-Bibliophile, CUTN for inviting me to write a brief memoir in honour of Dr Ravi to be published in the special issue of the Bibliophile, the newsletter of DLIS-CUTN. It is rightly said by the noted author, Dr Otuechere 'Champions are treasures that are full of wisdom, encouragement, provision, love, guidance, and empathy.' I sincerely wish Dr S Ravi a happy and peaceful life, and pray that he continues to be a champion, guiding the young professionals in their quest for professional zenith.

OUR GRATITUDE

Prof. Pravakar Rath
Sr. Professor & Head, DLIS
Mizoram University

Prof. Sabanayagam Ravi whom I know for the last three decades was first introduced to me at Annamalai Study Center, New Delhi and got the opportunity of interacting with him continuously till date. As a teacher of Annamalai University, he was associated with Open and Distance Learning programs and very much student centric in dealing with various problems of students and trying to solve to the maximum extent possible. Prof. Ravi throughout was

Dr. (Mrs.) Moorttimatee Rath
Deputy Librarian
NCERT, New Delhi

committed and devoted to his academic assignment and was one amongst the most popular teachers of Annamalai university. Prof. Ravi got the opportunity of being appointed as Professor of Library and Information Science at Central University of Tamil Nadu because of his excellent academic and research background and became Head, Dean, and Member of the Academic and Executive Council. Besides, because of his vast academic, research and administrative experience, he could be able to establish the Department at Central University of Tamil Nadu.

In course of time Dr (Mrs.) Moorttimatee Rath was introduced to Annamalai University and Central University of Tamil Nadu and extended her academic and professional cooperation and found Prof. Ravi as one of the most committed teacher with great passion for teaching, positive attitude besides a well known subject expert in different classification schemes.

Myself and Mrs. Rath join to express our gratitude on the day of his superannuation and felicitation function and pray almighty for his good health, long life and productive time in the years to come.

Prof. Pravakar Rath & Dr. Moorttimatee Rath

PROF. S. RAVI- A GEM OF A MAN

Dr. S. Srinivasaraghavan
Controller of Examinations (i/c) &
Professor & Head
Dept. of Library & Information
Science
Bharathidasan University

I am happy to know that the Department of Library and Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu, is bringing a special issue of its coveted newsletter-Bibliophile to facilitate Dr. S. Ravi, Professor and Dean of the School of Library and Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu. I appreciate your efforts to honour Professor. S. Ravi, on his superannuation, his long academic service, for which Prof. S. Ravi is very much deserved, as he has contributed significantly to the Library Information Science Profession and as a noble educational administrator. I have been observing him, as I have been associated with him since my university days, as he was an immediate senior in M. Lib. I. Sc program at Madurai Kamaraj University, which is my alma mater, above all, his academic calibre, professional traits, he is a gem of a man as he possess good values, leadership qualities and empathy towards his colleagues and students. I am very much delighted to be a part of this initiative to facilitate Dr. S. Ravi's prolonged health and happiness and to have a wonderful second inning.

Dr. S. Srinivasaraghavan

My Impressions on Prof. S. Ravi

Prologue

It is a great pleasure to know that the friends, students, scholars, colleagues, admirers and well-wishers of Prof. Dr. S. Ravi, have planned to felicitate him on the eve of his superannuation. I am happy to recollect my impressions on him who is superannuating on October 31st, 2022, as a faculty in the Department of Library and Information Science and Dean in the Central University of Tamilnadu (CUTN), Thiruvarur. Earlier he served in the Annamalai University, Chidambaram for nearly three decades in the Department of Library and Information Science, Directorate of Distance Education. He is known to me for the past three and half decades and I visited the departments both at Annamalai and CUTN several times on academic invitation. I observed him as a dedicated teacher and one of the most respected LIS professionals in the country.

His Positive Attitude

He considers all the happenings occurred either good or bad in a positive way. He motivates the students, researchers, and fellow professionals in a positive way. He is helpful to everyone in the field without looking his or her background of position. He is very unassuming personality both as a teacher and as an administrator in the university. No doubt, the library & information science community shower him with love and respect due to his positive nature. As a person, Prof. S, Ravi is

soft spoken, cultured and responsible.

His Academic record

He has a good academic and professional record which is an indicator of his teaching ability, managerial competence and service orientation. He is a member of various national professional associations. He travelled across the globe as a Coordinator for DDE programmes in Annamalai University. He is a prolific writer and contributed a number of articles in national and international journals and conferences, edited volumes and prepared course materials for various universities.

His Professional Network

He is a member of various national professional associations. A professional of profound experience he has been associated with a number of Universities as a member of Board of Studies, Board of Examiners, an Adjudicator, Evaluator, Resource person for the preparation of course materials and Councilor in distance education, Chair person in seminars, workshops, conferences, and so on. His dedication for the profession has captured the attention of many state universities' attentions. He excels in connecting with people and succeeds in forming a productive network among professionals.

Epilogue

Superannuation or retirement from service is routine event in one's life and Prof. S Ravi is not an exception to this phenomenon. Though he is retiring in October 2022 from the University service, I wish and strongly believe that he will not retire from the academic and professional world. My appreciation for the Members of the Festschrift Committee and also the Editorial Committee for having thought of organizing a felicitation function and presenting him a Festschrift. I wish him a happy, peaceful and healthy retired life. I congratulate all his researchers, fellow professionals and friends for having thought of bringing out the Festschrift and presenting to him during the felicitation function to mark his retirement. Myself and my family members pray the Lord Almighty to bestow on him and his family with a healthy, wealthy, peaceful and joyful retired life. May God bless him.

Prof. B. Ramesh Babu

Former Professor
Dept. of Library and Information Science
University of Madras, Chennai

Former Visiting Professor
Faculty of Informatics Maharakham
University, Thailand

GALLERY

Through the ages...

Hats off to Prof. S. Ravi

At the Beginning of a New Life

Though I had heard a lot about Prof. Ravi in the nineteen nineties mainly from the alumni of Annamalai University and my friends there, I had the occasion to meet him in person only in 2010 at the Department of Library and Information Science, Pondicherry University. His pleasing manners and friendly demeanor are captivating. That happened to be an auspicious occasion because we the opportunity to see each other thereafter on a number of times. Prof. Amudhavalli used to invite me as a visiting faculty at the Department of Library and Information Science, University of Madras and naturally that turned out to be our meeting place. Prof. Ravi would be there either as resource person for the Refresher Course or for the valuation of answer scripts. During one or two Refresher Courses in Library and Information Science, I could witness the love and regard for him maintained by his students.

I was somewhat elated when he joined as Professor in the newly formed Department of Library and Information Science of Central University Tamil Nadu (CUTN). I was very much interested in the progress of the Department which came up especially due to the fact that I happened to be a member of the Committee appointed for drafting the curriculum of the LIS course of CUTN. There is one more reason for my interest in the fledgling department. In the Committee Meeting, I expressed my view that it is better to fix the number of intake of students as 15, though other members were of the opinion that the admission should be restricted to 10, of course, based on the experience of full time LIS courses in some universities in Tamil Nadu. I took such a stand based on the experience at Pondicherry University. There I had seen that in the initial years, the number of students was low, but the number of applicants steadily went up. I was pretty sure that being a Central University, the facilities would be much better than state universities which in turn would attract many students. Ultimately, we unanimously decided to have a strength of 15 students.

My calculation was proved to be correct. I still remember that Prof. Ravi was a little bit worried because only 10 students were there in spite of his best efforts including the preparation of a very attractive brochure. However, he managed to fill the seats and now I understand that there is much rush for seats.

Kerala Library Association (KLA), the premier association of professional librarians in Kerala, organizes annual commemoration lecture in the name of Prof. K. A. Isaac, the doyen of Library Science education in Kerala and our revered Guru. Some of the previous speakers were Prof. K. S. Raghavan, Prof. Karisiddhappa, Prof. Amudhavalli, Dr. Jagdish Arora and an array of luminaries in the field. It was the affability, unassuming nature and scholarliness of Prof. Ravi that made me, as President of Kerala Library Association, to invite him for the lecture. He readily agreed to deliver the talk. I recollect that a large number of his previous students came to the venue of the lecture in Thiruvananthapuram to listen to him, to greet him and to exchange pleasantries with him.

Dr. Vijayakumar K P

President, Kerala Library Association
Former Head, DLIS &
Hon. Director, Centre for
Information Literacy Studies
University of Kerala
Thiruvananthapuram

To conclude I would like to say that it is sad to see you leave but the moments we all shared and the memories we made with you will always be remembered. On behalf of everyone, I wish you good luck. I am sure that you will find a new workplace and will surely reach greater heights. It is time to relax and enjoy himself. Life begins at retirement. Now he is as free as the breeze I wish him good health and happiness for the future. He will always be remembered for his hard work throughout the years. I wish him to enjoy his retirement !

A LETTER TO PROF.S.RAVI

Dear Prof. S Ravi

It is my pleasure to congratulate you on your retirement as Professor and Head, of the Department of Library and Information Science, at Central University of Tamil Nadu.

The Department was established in 2017 to provide professional education and training in the discipline of LIS. I believe that you are instrumental in organising the Department and introduce world class curriculum and state –of- the -art facilities in the Department. The rich experience and exposure you have earned from the previous organisation may be the source and inspiration to achieve these success. I had the opportunity to know your sincerity towards job and your academic calibre. I still remember the occasion when you made an invited talk in a programme organised by KLA. I really appreciate you for the honesty and hard work throughout the academic career.

Once again I congratulate you and offer all wishes to achieve more exciting positions in future too.

Prof. (Dr.) A. Gopikuttan

Former Professor & Director
School of Communication &
Information Science,
University of Kerala
Thiruvananthapuram

Yours Sincerely

Dr. A. Gopikuttan

PROF. S. RAVI - GOD'S GIFT

The first time I came to know about our beloved Prof. S. Ravi Garu, was when I was working as a Research Scholar at the Department of Library and Information Science, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam. And our Professor S. Ravi Garu, served as a Senior Faculty member of Annamalai University as Head, Dept. of the Library and Information Science. He was a very familiar and well-known Faculty among the Library Science in Indian Universities and Library Professionals and Librarians in Southern India.

Though he served a few years at the CUTN, no doubt, his selection as a CUTN, Thiruvavur as Professor, direct: is a "God's Gift" and Boon, to his Teaching Career and it is a precious and worthy service in his lifetime.

He is the founder Head and the first Dean School of Communication. He served in different positions at all academic levels. His contributions to the department on purchasing DDC and UDC schedules within a short period opened the research admission to M.Phil and Ph.D programmes. He envisaged the department with a future vision. All of us on the campus are very proud of your academic contributions to the department in general and the university in particular through attending his regular class teaching, research academic and administrative activities. Prof. Ravi's long experiences, knowledge, and teaching skills are attributed to his spontaneous lecturing in regular class work. Regarding his research experience, he was very popular as an Examiner for evaluating Ph.D. dissertations. He was a well-known personality in this profession in promoting academic research in Indian Universities.

Dr. Taddi Murali
Assistant Professor
DLIS, CUTN

I have observed that he was very prompt in positively appreciating the Ph.D works. He was a regular visitor to all most all the universities in southern India as an examiner for Ph.D viva-voce. It shows that his positive attitude, approach, and sense of understanding others is a perfect and excellent perception of Prof.Ravi.

I am a person who believes in the life cycle of human beings, i.e. Job, Service and Retirement. These are very routine steps in everyone's life.

Hence I do not believe in the concept of Goodbye or Farewell to our Prof. Ravi Garu. We will all miss you, Prof. Ravi Garu, from next month onwards. However, I can confidently say that your suggestions and advice have moulded us into good academic staff; now, we are ready to take up any intellectual challenge in the future. Sir, this farewell day is not the last day you will see each other. Let us promise that we will stay in touch with each other forever.

We have left no stone unturned and have put all our efforts into making this Farewell day a memorable one in your lifetime.

Life begins at Retirement...

Prof. Ravi is a well-known personality among library professionals and Library science teachers in India and abroad. Many of his students have occupied senior positions worldwide in various libraries and teaching institutions. Prof. Ravi is undoubtedly an exceptional teacher who has been involved in different activities that often went beyond the domain of his profession. A stage comes in a person's life when he takes stock of his achievements, particularly in the LIS profession. Dr. Ravi has been a Professor and a human being par excellence.

Prof. Ravi, whose life is a saga of activities and inspiration to others. Above all, he has been a philanthropist among LIS professionals as well. Dr. Ravi has created a different history. He had professional experience of 11 years at Annamalai University library and 33 years of post-graduate teaching and research. He also served as Professor for 16 years at Annamalai University and CUTN. He has been an inspiring

teacher in imparting theoretical and practical knowledge to LIS students. With his humble beginning, he touched greater heights professionally and socially and was loved by everyone. He has marked an incredible journey in the academic institutions and today is the day we have to bid farewell to him from this esteemed institution.

In this LIS field, he has worked so hard with great devotion. He was the epitome of simplicity and was praised for his selfless service in the institutions. It is my pleasure to describe his excellent nature and caring behaviour. He will always be an inspiration to everybody because of his dedication. His impression will always be in our hearts. There are endless words for him, and we will be forever grateful to him. So, I wish Prof. Ravi the best for his future.

I spent many valuable moments with him, which will be in my mind forever. He is not only a great friend but also a good son, father and husband. His approach to balancing both professional life and personal life is truly incredible. He never allowed his personal life to affect his workplace productivity and was always on a mission to make his project successful.

To conclude, I would like to say that it is sad to see you leave, but the moments we all shared and the memories we made with you will always be remembered. On behalf of everyone, I wish you good luck. I am sure you will find a new workplace and reach greater heights.

It is time to relax and enjoy himself. Life begins at retirement. Now he is as free as the breeze. I wish him good health and happiness in the future. He will always be remembered for his hard work throughout the years.

I wish him to enjoy his retirement !

Dr. K. Nithyanandam

President, Madras Library Association

Former Director & University Librarian
Anna University &
Prof. & Head, DLIS,
Hindustan University

A FAREWELL NOTE

My memories about Ravi sir starts from a phone call. After my interview in CUTN in the last week of May, I got busy with my daily chaos as a College Librarian in Coimbatore and I almost forgot about the interview itself. It was in the last week of July, I received a phone call from an unknown number asking “is it Dr. Dhanyasree?” I said “Yes”.

“Madam, this is from Dept. of LIS, CUTN. When are you joining?”

Me (not understanding what he is talking about for a moment): “I’m sorry, I didn’t get you?”

“You’ve been selected as an Assistant Professor in CUTN. When are you joining?”

Me (strongly believing that somebody is pranking me): “Are you kidding?”

“Ohh...you didn’t know? Please check your inbox; you would have received an e-mail. I’m Prof. Ravi calling from the Dept. of LIS”.

Me (still not digesting): “Okay sir, I’ll check my mail and call you back”.

Dr. V. K. Dhanyasree

Assistant Professor
DLIS, CUTN

Disconnecting the call, checking the mail, finding the appointment order, taking a few minutes to take it all in, and then it was a rollercoaster of emotions - extremely happy for the order, at the same time feeling ashamed for how I talked to Ravi sir, regretting it, totally confused what to do, not knowing whether to laugh or cry.....

Then I called him back: “Sir, I’m sorry. I just saw it. I thought somebody was making fun of me, that’s why I talked like that”.

Ravi sir: “Ohh (laughing).....no problem madam.....when are you joining?”

Then onwards until joining here in CUTN, I have been regularly making phone calls to Ravi sir to get guidance regarding relieving from the previous institution and other technical matters related to that.

At this juncture, I wish him good health, happiness and a peaceful life, and hope that the personal bond will persist. I also hope that he will continue to be as energetic and active in the academic sphere as he was always.

Dr. Anila Sulochana

Assistant Professor
DLIS, CUTN

YOU LEAVE BEHIND A GOOD LEGACY...

My association with CUTN was started with a phone call from Dr. S Ravi and it was really a welcoming one. In most of my interactions I found him extremely affable. As a teacher and mentor, you leave behind a good legacy and I hope this journey will continue to another level with your great enthusiasm.

PROF. S. RAVI- A TRUE TEACHER

The biggest lessons don't come from books but from a teacher like you. You helped us to know more about the Father of Library Science. I still remember having helped me during my PhD viva-voce. Thank you so much for your kindness, wisdom, and positivity. Thank you for taking the time to listen, encourage, and share. You made a real difference in the lives of the students you taught.

Congratulation and many warm wishes.

Dr. Elavazhagan K

Dr. Elavazhagan K

Librarian & Chief Knowledge Officer
Indian Institute of Management
Tiruchriappalli

Dr. J K Vijayakumar & Manju Vijayakumar

Former Strategic Information Advisor
King Abdullah University of S & T , SA
Alumni, Annamalai University

REMINISCENSE OF FORMER STUDENTS

The first thing about Dr. Ravi sir that comes to my mind is his smiling face and then his way of having humble conversations. He is the tallest teacher in our department at Annamalai University, still, he stands taller with his successful career and great contributions to the LIS profession. His interesting lessons taught us the important role of librarians in enriching the society they serve and being customer oriented. We all should get inspired by his personal commitment to transforming his professional life which grew from an entry-level employee to a Dean level. He not only guides and teaches but alsoinspires all of us as role model. We wish him a happy retirement life.

GALLERY

Annamalai Days

Reminiscences in Honour of Prof. S. Ravi

2020-22 Batch M. Lib. I. Sc. Students

Vijaya Kumar R

We are pleased to present this Festschrift, which honours Professor S.Ravi. He worked in various institutions, and finally, he came to the Central University of Tamil Nadu. He has more than 40 years of service as a library science scholar. The Post Graduate students of the Department of Library & Information Science batch (2020–2022) of Central University of Tamil Nadu have contributed this paper to the beloved Prof.S.Ravi sir. Besides being an avid researcher, Ravi sir has channeled his enthusiasm for education and has shown to be an exceptional teacher, introducing thousands of LIS students to the beauty of the Library and inspiring many of them to continue their education and research. Studying the subjects, he first piqued their interest. Many state and international graduate and postgraduate students have joined Ravi sir's research due to his extensive and in-depth scientific expertise, excellent reputation, and enthusiasm for Library and information science. We are delighted to have our sir as a lecturer for us, and we have had a positive experience with him. He encourages students to think critically and come up with original solutions to problems and questions, which, in my opinion, is the primary responsibility of any lecturer or instructor. He never reprimands but corrects. Thus we never felt anxious about getting the answers right or wrong throughout his lesson. Instead, we used all of our brains to provide creative solutions. Even when we create noise in the computer lab where his cabin is attached, he only smiled but never reprimanded us. Of course, he will correct students' mistakes, but sir knows when to correct and where to correct, and we have never seen him being rude to anyone at any place in the department or outside of it except in a case when someone makes derogation of Library Science apart from that sir is very hospitable to students. Service in the field of library and information science spanning four decades, including 11 years in the University Library at Annamalai University, where he received training in all library procedures, including reprography and archives management. Twenty-nine years of experience in postgraduate teaching, research, and academic administration in the field of library and information science. He began his teaching career in these twenty-nine years, working as a lecturer, reader, and professor.

His appointment as professor and department head of library and information science at Central University of Tamil Nadu Thiruvavur began in 2017. In addition, he worked for five years as a mentor for the international collaborative programs for the Commonwealth Diploma in Youth Development Work and Commonwealth Certificate in Youth Development Work with the Commonwealth Secretariat, London. Moreover, he guided and Awarded twenty Ph.D. candidates and forty-five M.Phil candidates. And also guided several Postgraduate students. On the research side, Ravi Sir has published over forty articles in peer-reviewed national and international journals. He also got accolades from various professional organizations at the state and national levels.

We are so delighted to get our sir as a lecturer for us the experience which we have with the sir charming he is the one who makes students think and answer to a question and problem to a solution in a creative way which is the determination of any lecturer/Teacher to do for their students, in his class. In his exams, we used to say the answers without the fear of right or wrong because if it is wrong, he will teach what is right, and if it is correct, he will appreciate it. Still, he never daunts for a wrong answer. We have never seen him so serious anywhere in the department and also out of the department, even when we are disorganized in the computer lab where his cabin is attached. He just gave a smile but never reprimanded.

Uday Kiran

Aysha Mahira C. M.

I am from the so-called 'Corona batch,' and the time we had with our teachers and University was merely months. Even if it were just months, the impact that each teacher created in our minds was tremendous. Amidst the confusion and chaos, Ravi sir always gave us a helping hand. He always made sure that we never had any troubles in our studies or with any facilities inside University. He is the epitome of knowledge and yet the most humble person I've ever seen. A person so immersed in the field of Library science and an ardent devotee of Dr.S.R.Ranganathan. I still remember his speeches. Whenever he gets a chance to speak of

Dr. Ranganathan, his words flow like an endless river, his heart filled with respect and admiration. Holi, Ugadi, Farewell. He never failed to celebrate with us, gave us his wise words, and shared his beautiful memories. He has such a nostalgic and sweet voice that whenever we get a chance, we always request his songs, and never even once has he declined us. One can learn a lot from his life and character. To be like him, even a hundred years wouldn't be enough. I wish him happy and fruitful days throughout his life.

In 2020-22, we were an online batch because of Corona, so we are called Corona Batch. We don't know much about online education, But on the First day of Ravi sir's class, am nervous. What does he ask? What did I reply? Lots of questions. That moment was unforgettable. Such a lovely person. Come forward and communicate don't be shy and afraid. We all are friends. These are some words of Dr.Ravi, sir. He has a big hand behind our success, Like our parents. "A Good Teacher is the one who Inspires students. He teaches easily. He treats every student equally. He pays attention to every student. A Good teacher is Dr.Ravi".

Greeshma

Yazhini R.

Before I say anything else, I want to express my sincere gratitude to Ravi Sir for being a magnificent and passionate professor. He always welcomes us with the words of my dear friends, and I am fortunate to have him. When I think of Ravi sir's lectures, my mind immediately goes to our online DDC classes and his lecture hours. Even though it was online, he is the only person who can teach DDC the way he can. His commitment to the lecture constantly leaves us in awe. He never failed to entertain and enchant us with his singing. The kindness and support he showed us are beyond words. Even though we all split up, his advice

his advice has never failed to influence our lives. We must thank him for his tireless efforts, sincerity, and patience while teaching. I also pray that all of your students will make excellent use of the talents they have learned from you. And, I believe your fame at our university will never fade. Sincerely thank you for everything, Sir.

Aishwarya M.

Ravi sir was our HOD when we joined the course. I want to share how ecstatic I was when sir welcomed us into the department with a smile. It was like a homecoming for hostellers. Though I'm a hosteller, I felt like I'm in my home. He is that welcoming. I can say that he changed my approach toward the subject and the importance of persistence in gaining knowledge. I can firmly say that he is a phenomenal teacher. Because of him, our interest and responsibility to study have increased even during online classes. Thank you so much for making the subject accessible and understandable, which I was worried about disliking, a

class I was always excited to attend. Sir truly made my last semester one of the best I have ever had, and sir was my guide. His assistance helped me to a great extent to accomplish my dissertation effectively. I want to show gratitude for your patience and for being optimistic towards us, which made us ask questions without any fear and pushed us to the creative corner. Also, thank you for creating an environment where we aren't allowed to succeed but also to fail. Students thrive when students have the freedom to imagine, you gave us that, sir. Thank you, sir.

When I hear Dr. S. Ravi sir, the smiling face and sir's words "don't hesitate yourself" comes to my mind. Sir wants to make us comfortable in online classes during corona. Although we only had classes at the university for a few months, every day was extraordinary and a favorite. We celebrated Holi, Ugadi, and farewell. Ravi sir's presence in all of that is indescribable. A song by sir is a must if there is a department program. Sir used to sing old Tamil songs. Sir wants students to be more active in his class. When he asks a question, he always says, "whether your answer is right or wrong, don't hesitate even if the answer is correct or wrong ."He wants his students to be more active and confident. I wish him all the best in his entire life

D. Adhirai

My wonderful mentor Ravi, sir, I do not know where I would be without you. You made a significant difference in my career. All those times have gone the extra mile for me. The notes and the kind words helped give me a sense of hope. Your belief in me makes me believe in myself. Thank you! You are awesome! I was lucky to have you as my professor and even more fortunate to have you as a mentor. You were my mentor for my dissertation. And I was so happy about that. Accept my heartfelt gratitude for your time, support, and patience. Thank you for imparting skills that have shaped my career and professional life. Your teaching style is very different, friendly, and accessible. Learning has meant so much

to me. I can never really thank you enough. I honestly can't express how lucky I feel to have had the opportunity to learn from the Outstanding lecture From weakness to strength, from grass to grace, and from nothing to something. You are a big inspiration Role model for me, sir. The knowledge you have imparted to me has also been a great asset throughout my career and personal life. Sir, from your smile. I always admire the songs you sing during festival times. You will be my favourite teacher. My batch is the last batch for you. I am the luckiest student. I am missing you a lot, sir. Thank you for helping me learn how to attain my goals and overcome any difficulties, sir.

Dr.S.Ravi sir's impact on the pandemic batch is indescribable. Whether it is the online or offline classes he made sure that we had a great time learning about the subject. We had the opportunity to celebrate some of the good times in CUTN with sir. His aura and the incredible support he had for everyone in the department will be cherished forever. We are grateful to get some really good moments of our life with sir. He always had a positive outlook on life and encouraged us to come forward to do our deeds. His spontaneity and knowledge have made him stand out, and all his achievements result from his hard work. But always, his personality has set a benchmark for everyone. He was always chivalrous and had a great rapport with each of us. We are so happy to have known him and to be his students. Even after years, we will remember him for her persona, which made him so special to all of us.

Karthika

Sarmishta Raghavan

In addition to being an excellent teacher, Professor Ravi is also a talented singer. During several occasions like Ugadi, Holi, and farewell time, we had a great time listening to his beautiful songs and excellent speech, which we still remember. We genuinely believe that the time we spent with him was highly beneficial. He had some magical power that he was able to seize the attention of every student. His classical melodies were a huge hit among our LIS family, and we all loved his music very much. He never missed an occasion to showcase his talent because he was such a man. The song he performed at the farewell ceremony was quite sad because it was the final song for our class, and we would never get to hear it again.

G R E A T G U R U

Respected Sir,

I am honoured and privileged that I got an opportunity of around five years to work under your supervision Sir. I have always felt very comfortable working with you, seeing you transforming our Department of Library and Information Science from scratch to what it is now. Your Leadership was instrumental in shaping our department scaling new heights, and progressing well. I have learnt many things from you, Sir especially advising me on how to succeed in life and also quoting this frequent word "Hard and Honest work" which inspired me to do well in my life and career. You are a great Guru, Motivator, Teacher, Gentleman, Well Wisher and a Great Singer. It is impossible to forget you and your contribution. Thanks for all your guidance and kind support.

Ms. M. Chithra
Computer Operator
DLIS, CUTN

An era of outstanding service has come to an end. Sir, you have imparted great values to your students and me apart from education alone. I hope you now enjoy all the hobbies you had to sacrifice during your time in teaching.

The knowledge you have shared with me is priceless, and I will remember your valuable lessons for the rest of my life. It is indeed immeasurable for the time and effort you've put into teaching. May God's endless blessings be upon you today and always.

Happy Retirement Sir!

M Chithra

GALLERY

DLIS Functions

Bibliometric Portrait of Prof. S. Ravi

A Distinguished Professor of Library and Information Science

Rima Hazarika & K. G. Sudhier

Research Scholar

Assistant Professor

DLIS - CUTN

Introduction

Quantitative documentation of an individual scientist's performance as an information-generating unit has broad impacts on the domain of scientometrics. A bibliometric portrait deals with the quantitative (how many publications) and qualitative (where they are published) documentation of science communication by a given scientist. Scientific publications have provided the best available basis for measuring the results of individual scientists, as there is a good correlation between the scientists' eminence and their sustained academic publications. Scientometric studies are highly valued by historians of science, biographers of scientists, administrators of scientific establishments, science policymakers, R&D managers, educators, scientometrics, young scientists, documentalists, information scientists, and science journalists.

Prof. S. Ravi- Biographical Sketch

Prof. (Dr.) S. Ravi, Central University of Tamil Nadu (CUTN) is a dynamic LIS Professor well known throughout India. He has been working as Professor at CUTN since 2017. Previously, he served for 30 years at Annamalai University, reaching the position of Professor and Head, Dept. of the Library and Information Science. Prof. Ravi has published more than 150 research articles in National/International Journals and Conference and Seminar Proceedings. Apart from this, he has authored two books and nine edited books to his credit. He has delivered more than 120 invited lectures in various institutions. 22 researchers obtained their Ph.D. degrees under his guidance. He has received the Best Teacher award twice; he was honored with the Life Time Achievement award at the national level by the Madras Library Association (MALA) and Society for the Advancement of Library and Information Science (SALIS). For academic purposes, he has visited eight countries-Australia, Singapore, Malaysia, Mauritius, United Arab Emirates, Thailand, Brunei, and Sri Lanka.

Objectives

The specific objectives of this study are: -

- To find out the bibliographic forms of contributions
- To study the year-wise distribution of journal articles
- To study the year-wise distribution of book chapters
- To find out the year-wise contributions and productivity
- To identify the peak productivity age
- To explore the authorship pattern in Prof. S. Ravi's research publications.
- To determine the average yearly contributions
- To identify core journals
- To find out the length of pages wise distribution of article
- To find out the year-wise citation from google scholar
- To identify the publication of the book chapter
- To know the geographical distribution of conferences.
- To identify subject wise distribution of articles.

Methodology

In the present study, the data has been collected from Google scholar, the website of the CUTN and the profile. Prof. S. Ravi. Data collected from these sources are subjected to bibliometric analysis using variables such as year, productive age, chronological age, authorship, and publication of the conferences. All data were manually processed, tabulated, and analyzed with Microsoft Excel to meet the objectives using bibliometric indicators and percentage analysis.

Data Analysis Bibliographic Forms of Contributions

The contributions made by Prof. S. Ravi, as analyzed from the available resources, have been tabulated in the Figure1. Out of the 116 publications, the major contribution has been on Journal articles, i.e., 47 (40.51%), followed by Book Chapter, i.e., 43 (37.06%) publications. This is followed by 14 (12.06%) Conference (National and International), 7 (6.03%) Edited book, 3 (2.58%) Reviews articles and 2 (1.72%) Research Project.

Year-Wise Distribution of Journal Articles

Table 1 shows all the publications of Prof. S. Ravi, ranging from 2000 to 2020. The peak year in his publication history is 2011 with 8 (17.02%) publications, and the second highest is 2012 and 2014, with 6 (12.76%) publications. The third positions are in 2008 with 4 (8.51%) publications and fourth positions are in 2007, 2010, 2015, 2016 and 2018 with 6.38%) publications and fifth positions are in 2009 and 2019 with 2 (4.25%) publications and the least positions is in 2000, 2013, 2017 and 2020 with 1 (2.12%) publication, respectively.

Table 1 Year-wise distribution of Articles

Sl. No.	Year	International Journals	National Journals	Total of Articles	Percentage (%)
1.	2000	0	1	1	2.12
2.	2007	0	3	3	6.38
3.	2008	3	1	4	8.51
4.	2009	1	1	2	4.25
5.	2010	1	2	3	6.38
6.	2011	3	5	8	17.02
7.	2012	3	3	6	12.76
8.	2013	1	0	1	2.12
9.	2014	3	3	6	12.76
10.	2015	1	2	3	6.38
11.	2016	2	1	3	6.38
12.	2017	1	0	1	2.12
13.	2018	3	0	3	6.38
14.	2019	2	0	2	4.25
15.	2020	1	0	1	2.12
Total		25	22	47	100.00

Table 2 Year-wise distribution of Book Chapter

Sl. No.	Year	Book Chapter	Percentage (%)
1.	2001	1	2.38
2.	2007	1	2.38
3.	2009	7	16.66
4.	2010	3	7.14
5.	2011	3	7.14
6.	2012	1	2.38
7.	2013	5	11.90
8.	2014	4	9.52
9.	2015	0	0
10.	2016	2	4.76
11.	2017	0	0
12.	2018	4	9.52
13.	2019	4	9.52
14.	2020	4	9.52
15.	2021	1	2.38
Total		40	

Year-Wise Distribution of Book Chapters

Table 2 shows all the publications of the book chapter, ranging from 2001 to 2021. The peak year in his publication history is 2009, with 7 (16.66%) publications, and the second highest is 2013, with 5 (11.90%) publications, respectively. Out of 42 publication, two chapters has not been identified in the year of publishing.

Year-Wise Distribution and Productive Life

By analyzing the collected data, we found the entire productive life of Prof. S. Ravi to be 21 years. The productivity age, the contributor's age, and publication details are shown in Table 3. His productive age began in 2000 at the age of 43 years. He published the highest number of research papers in 2011, at the productive age of 12 and the chronological age of 54. The second

highest number of research papers published was in 2012 and 2014 at 13 and 15 and the chronological age of 55 and 57. The third highest number of research papers was in 2008, at the productivity age of 9 and the chronological age of 51, respectively.

Peak Productivity Age

The contributions of Prof. S. Ravi are grouped into five blocked years. The productive age and the chronological age are comprised together. Table 5 shows that the peak productivity age stands between 11 to 15 years of productive age and between 53-57 years of chronological age.

Table 4 Peak Productivity Age

Sl. No.	Productive Age	Chronological Age	Year	No. of Contributions	Percentage (%)
1	01-05	44	2000	1	1.47
2	06-10	50-52	2007-2009	9	6.47
3	11-15	53-57	2010-2014	24	51.06
4	16-20	58-62	2015-2019	12	25.53
5	21-25	63	2020	1	1.47
Total				47	100.00

Table 3 Year-wise distribution and productive life

Sl. No.	Year	No of Articles	Cumulative No.	Productivity Age	Age of Chronological
1.	2000	1	1	1	43
2.	2007	3	4	8	50
3.	2008	4	8	9	51
4.	2009	2	10	10	52
5.	2010	3	13	11	53
6.	2011	8	21	12	54
7.	2012	6	27	13	55
8.	2013	1	28	14	56
9.	2014	6	34	15	57
10.	2015	3	37	16	58
11.	2016	3	40	17	59
12.	2017	1	41	18	60
13.	2018	3	44	19	61
14.	2019	2	46	20	62
15.	2020	1	47	21	63
Total		47			63

Authorship Pattern of Journal Articles

Table 5 shows that only 14 (29.78%) articles are a single author, and two authors' publications contribute 23 (48.93%) to the total publication. Three authors have contributed to 10 (21.27%) of the total publications. Therefore, most of the publication was done by double author.

Table 5 Authorship Pattern of Journal Articles

Sl. No	No. of Authors	No. of Articles	Percentages (%)
1	Single Author	14	29.78
2	Two Authors	23	48.93
3	Three Authors	10	21.27
Total		47	100.00

Author Collaboration in the Journal Articles

Table 6 shows the most prolific authors associated with Prof. S. Ravi in national and international journal articles. The most active authors were K. Murugan, who topped the list with 7 articles, followed by S. Surianarayanan with 4.

Table 6 Top Author Collaboration in Journal Articles

Sl. No.	Authors	Total No. of articles
1.	S. Ravi	47
2.	K. Murugan	7
3.	S. Surianarayanan	4
4.	L. Mohan Kumar	3
5.	K. Maheswari	3
6.	N. O. Natarajan	3
7.	R. Sarangapani	2
8.	J. Vasanthi	2
9.	Revathi R.	2
10.	K. Saravanan	2
11.	S. Thanuskodi	2
12.	P. Ravichandran	2
13.	D. Manimegalai	2
14.	M. Madhavi	2
15.	V. Mohan	2

Average Yearly Contributions

The average yearly contributions of Prof. S. Ravi during his productive life are calculated using the formula.

$$AYC = \frac{\text{Total Contribution}}{\text{Total Productivity Age}} = \frac{47}{21} = 2.23$$

The average yearly contribution of Prof. S. Ravi is 2.23, which means, on average, he has published more than two papers in a year during the period 2000 to 2020.

Top Ranked Journals

Table 7 shows that 47 articles have been published in 23 journals. The Asian Journal of Information Science and Technology and the Journal of Advanced in Library and Information Science tops the list with 6 (12.76%) contributions, followed by Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services with 5 (10.63%) contributions. The Journal of Research in Librarianship and Technology and Library Progress (International) has 4 (8.51%) contributions. Journal of Library Advancements has 3 (6.38%) followed by Indian Journal of Information Science and Services and International Journal of Library and Information Studies with 2 (4.25%) contributions, and the rest 15 journals have 1 contribution, respectively.

Table 7. Ranked List of top Journals

Sl. No	Journals	Rank	No. of Papers	Percentage (%)
1.	Asian Journal of Information Science and Technology	1	6	12.76
2.	Journal of Advanced in Library and Information Science	2	6	12.76
3.	Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services	3	5	10.63
4.	Journal of Research in Librarianship	4	4	8.51
5.	Library Progress (International)	5	4	8.51
6.	Journal of Library Advancements	6	3	6.38
7.	Indian Journal of Information Science and Services	7	2	4.25
8.	International Journal of Library and Information Studies	8	2	4.25

Length of Pages Wise Distribution of Article

Table 8. Page Length of the Articles

Year	Pages				Total	Percentage (%)
	01-05	06-10	11-15	16-20		
2000	0	1	0	0	1	2.22
2007	1	1	1	0	3	6.66
2008	1	3	0	0	4	8.88
2009	0	2	0	0	2	4.44
2010	3	0	0	0	3	6.66
2011	2	5	0	0	7	15.5
2012	0	6	0	0	6	13.3
2013	0	1	0	0	1	2.22
2014	0	5	0	1	6	13.33
2015	1	1	1	0	3	6.66
2016	1	0	2	0	3	6.66
2017	1	0	0	0	1	2.22
2018	0	0	3	0	3	6.66
2019	1	0	1	0	2	4.44
Total	11	25	8	1	45	100.00
Percentage (%)	24.44	55.55	17.77	2.22	100	

Table 8. shows the page length of articles reveals that during the period under study, the majority articles length of pages 25 (55.55%) articles publication from 06 -10 pages. Then 11 (24.44%) articles were published from 01-05, then 8 (17.77%) articles published from 11-15 pages and remaining one articles were from 16-20 pages.

Year-Wise Citation from Google Scholar

Figure 2. Citations per year

Figure 2 represents the year-wise citations of the publications by Prof. S. Ravi ranging from 2007 to 2022, excluding the years 2000.

Book Chapter Publication

Table 9. show that out of 43 book chapters, the highest number of books has been published by the Dept. of Library & Information Science, Annamalai University. The second highest number of book chapters have been published by the Department of Library and Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur. The third highest number has been published by Central Library, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur, and IGI Global Information Science Reference, respectively.

Table 9. Publication of top Book Chapters

Sl. No.	Book Chapters	Total Number
1	Dept. of Library & Information Science, Annamalai University	9
2	Department of Library and Information Science, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur	4
3	Central Library, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur	2
4	IGI Global Information Science Reference	2
5	Aavishkar Publishers, Distributors, Jaipur	1
6	Alagappa University, Karaikudi.	1
7	Almighty Book Company Chennai	1
8	Bibliometric & Informetric Research Group (BIRG), UNSW	1
9	E.S. Abdul Rahman Crescent Engineering College, Chennai & S.A.I.S., Chennai.	1
10	Central Library, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore	1

Geographical Distribution of Conferences

Country-wise Distribution of Conferences

Table 10. shows that the highest number of conferences originated from India (78.57%), and the second highest number of conferences originated from Australia, Thailand, and Sri Lanka with 1 (7.14%).

State-wise contribution of conferences from India

Table No. 11 shows that out of 11 states, Tamil Nadu emerged at the top with a maximum of 8 conferences, followed by Karnataka, New Delhi, and Mizoram having 1 (9.09%) of the total number of conferences.

Subject Distribution of Articles

Table 12 shows that most contributions appeared under Metrics Study 14 (29.78%). The next position is taken by ICT 11 (23.40%), followed by Library Professional 7 (14.89%). The fourth position is taken by digital and resource and services 5 (10.63%). Knowledge Management and Physical Education are in the fifth position of 2 (4.25%). And the least is taken by E-Resources 1(2.12%).

Table 10. Country Wise Distribution of Conferences

Sl. No.	Name of the country	Total No. of Conferences	Rank	Percentages (%)
1	India	11	1	78.57
2	Australia	1	2	7.14
3	Thailand	1	2	7.14
4	Sri Lanka	1	2	7.14
Total		14		100.00

Table 11. State-wise contribution of conferences from India

Sl. No.	Name of the State	Total No. of Conferences	Rank	Percentages (%)
1	Tamil Nadu	8	1	72.72
2	Karnataka	1	2	9.09
3	New Delhi	1	2	9.09
4	Mizoram	1	2	9.09
Total		11		100.00

Table 12 Subject Distribution of Articles

Sl. No.	Subject	Total	Percentage (%)
1	Metrics Studies	14	29.78
2	ICT applications	11	23.40
3	Library Professional	7	14.89
4	Digital libraries	5	10.63
5	Resource and services	5	10.63
6	Knowledge Management	2	4.25
7	Physical Education	2	4.25
8	E-resources	1	2.12
Total		47	100.00

Conclusion

This study highlighted the profile of Prof. S. Ravi’s contributions and academic productivity according to the biological age, collaborative pattern and rise and fall of authorship status in the productivity curve, dispersion by publication channel, and other characteristics. The data has been collected from Google scholar and the website of the Central University of Tamil Nadu. Prof. S. Ravi has contributed outstanding work in Library and Information Science and is honored with numerous awards. He mentored many students and scholars to obtain their academic degrees under his guidance and supervision throughout his life. Prof. S. Ravi has visited many countries for educational purposes. Based on his research publications, he was more collaborative in his work. And Prof. S. Ravi will always be a source of inspiration for the youngsters in this profession.

மகிழ்ச்சியை பங்கு பெரும் தருணம்

எனக்கும் ரவி ஐயா அவருக்கும் உள்ள உறவு கடலை விட பெரியது. தொலை தூர கல்வி இயக்கத்தில் அவருடன் சேர்ந்து நான் ஆரம்பித்த பழக்கம் எனக்கு ஒரு நல்ல அடி தளத்தை ஏற்படுத்தியது.

நாங்கள் வகுப்பு எடுக்க பல முறை டெல்லி, கொல்கத்தா, பெங்களூர், சேலம், சென்னை, மதுரை, கோயமுத்தூர் செல்வோம் அப்போது ஐயா உடன் தங்கி இருந்து நான் கற்று கொண்ட பாடங்கள் அனுபவித்த சந்தோசங்கள் என்னாலும் மறக்க முடியாது அது ஒரு இனிமையான தருணம்.

எனக்கு ஒரு நல்ல ஆசானாக , வழிகாட்டியாக, நண்பனாக, சகோதரனாக, இன்று வரை இருந்து வரும் முனைவர் பேராசிரியர் S.ரவி அவர்கள் வயதின் அடிப்படையில் 31.10.2022 அன்று ஓய்வு பெற்று , அவரும் , அவரது துணைவியாரும் மணநிம்மதியோடும், உடல் ஆரோக்கியத்தோடும் நீடோடி வாழ எல்லாம் வல்ல இறைவனை பிறாத்திக்கிறேன்.

நம் உறவு எள்ளவும் குறையாமல் இருக்க அந்த இறைவனையே வேண்டுகிறேன்

மகிழ்ச்சி மகிழ்ச்சி மகிழ்ச்சி
என்றும் அன்புடன்

முனைவர் . இரா. நடராஜன்

அலைகள் ஓய்வதில்லை

Ms. Tamil Bharathi T. K.
M.Lib.I.Sc Student
2018-20 Batch
DLIS, CUTN

இளநிலை இனிமையாக நிறைவுற
முதுநிலை எதிலென முடிவுறா நிலை.....

“CUTN’ ல் இருந்து ரவி பேசறம்மா” என்றொலித்த
முதல் ஒலி – முதுநிலையின் முதல் ஒளி !

ஆங்கிலமென்பதாலே ஆயிரம் அடி பதுங்கியவளை
அரவணைத்து அடிமேல் அடிவைத்து
தொடுவானம் தொடும்பூரம் என என்னை
சிகரமேற்றி அழகு பார்த்தவர் !!
இக்கதிரவனின் கரங்கள் என்னை
வெற்றிமழையில் வாகைசூட வைத்தது....

பல்கலைகழகத்தின் புதிய கலாச்சாரத்தில்
தடுமாறிய நட்புகளுக்கிடையே
தடம் மாறாமல் என்னை தடம் பதிக்க வைத்தவர் !

துறை தாண்டிய உதவிகளை
நோக்கிய நொடியில் துணை
நின்று உவகையடைய செய்தவர் !!

வரிகளுக்குள் வரையறுத்து விடயியலா
நூலகத்துறையின் வைரம்,
ஓய்வு பெற்றாலும் ஒளிவீசிக் கொண்டும்,
நம்மை வழிநடத்திக் கொண்டே....இருக்கும்

பணியிலிருந்து ஓய்வு பெற்றாலும்
நூலகத்துறையில் என்றென்றும் அவரின்

GALLERY

FAMILY

தமிழ்நாடு மத்தியப்
பஸ்கலைக்கழகம்

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तमिलनाडु केन्द्रीय
विश्वविद्यालय